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3D-printed packed bed reactor for continuous catalytic hydrogenation of nitroaromatic compounds

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ABSTRACT

Aromatic amines (AAMs) are essential compounds for producing a wide range of industrial and pharmaceutical products. However, traditional synthesis methods using nitroaromatic compounds (NACs) pose environmental and health risks due to byproduct contamination and the carcinogenic nature of NACs. In this context, this study introduces a novel catalyst containing rhenium (*Re*) active sites. While this approach does not eliminate the carcinogenic risks associated with NACs, it aims to improve process efficiency. The catalyst, synthesized within a styrene-based matrix functionalized with 1,1'-carbonyldiimidazole, combines high affinity for NACs with the catalytic prowess of *Re* that may be also a tool in achieving process selectivity. Characterization via XPS and HRTEM confirmed the presence of highly dispersed *Re* species within the polymer matrix. The catalyst demonstrated superior activity in batch hydrogenation of various NACs, achieving high conversion rates. A 3D-printed packed bed reactor (PBR) was then developed for continuous flow-mode reduction of 4-nitrophenol (4-NP), achieving significant processing capacity and highlighting its potential for scalable applications. This innovative approach not only addresses environmental concerns associated with NACs but also enhances the efficiency of AAM production, presenting a viable solution for industrial processes.

1. Introduction

Aromatic amines (AAMs) are the key building blocks for the manufacturing of a variety of socially and industrially important products. These include photographic films, corrosion retarders, polymers, herbicides, dyes, and drug formulations [1–4]. The latter are especially important, as aromatic amines are the key substrates for the production of large-scale pharmaceuticals, including paracetamol, ibuprofen, bicalutamide (Casodex) and nilutamide (Nilandron tablet), linezolid (antibiotic for Gramme-positive bacteria resistant Gram-positive bacteria), and fosamprenavir, the anti-HIV drug, which has also been found to be effective in the treatment of COVID-19 [5–8].

The industrial synthesis of aromatic amines (AAMs) typically involves the reduction of structurally analogous nitroaromatic compounds (NACs) using stoichiometric reducing agents such as $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_4$, Fe, Sn, or Zn in NH_4OH [9]. Alternatively, NACs can be reduced on metal oxide

catalysts with H_2 gas as the reducing agent [5]. However, both approaches face significant challenges, including limited process selectivity and byproduct-related contamination [5,9]. Furthermore, NACs are classified as high-priority risk chemicals by the American Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) due to their carcinogenic potential and hazardous nature [10,11]. These considerations emphasize the need for developing highly effective and selective catalytic processes to improve the efficiency and sustainability of AAM production while minimizing environmental risks, and the present study may be a step towards it.

Recently, nanotechnology-based strategies for the reduction of NACs have gained considerable attention. The reason for this is the well-documented efficiency of a variety of nanomaterials (NMs), such as Au, Ag, Pt, and Pd nanoparticles (NPs) in the reduction of NACs [12–18]. Further, the nanoparticles of d-block elements, can prefer $-\text{NO}_2$ group over other moieties, hence, the application thereof may contribute to the process selectivity in real life scenarios [15]. However, issues such as the

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limited stability of NPs, the tendency to aggregate, the difficulty of separation, as well as the possible contamination by NPs [19] hinder the applicability of these materials in processes related to the synthesis of AAMs from wasted NACs. In this context, the main premise of this work is to propose a unique catalytic separation process that enables simultaneous reduction of NACs and production of AAMs in a flow-mode system. The authors of the present research hypothesise that, by tailoring a suitable heterogeneous catalyst, it may be possible to achieve this dual effect.

Hence, within the present work, we propose a unique catalytic bed, based on a previously developed nanocomposite catalyst [20] with catalytically active *Re* sites. The proposed solution bases on ReNPs which is emerging nanomaterial revealing the ability to form a variety of catalytically active species [21], and the ability to form catalytically active *Re* sub-nanomaterial clusters [20]. These properties make ReNPs tunable, and highly efficient catalysts recently proven to be a perfect fit for hydrogenation reactions [22]. Within this context, in our previous work [20] we have developed a new heterogeneous catalyst containing *Re* active sites, loaded and stabilized on specially designed anion exchange resins. The so-prepared catalysts were successful in batch processes of NACs hydrogenations, however, it is hypothesized that its morphology (suspension copolymer) may grant ease of operation by limiting hydrodynamic pressures in flow-mode systems. This, linked with the high catalytic activity attributed to the *Re*, and high affinity of styrene-based matrix towards NACs [20,23] should make the developed catalyst a perfect catalytic bed for a packed bed reactor (PBR) aimed at continuous, flow-mode NACs processing.

Within the present study, catalytic bed based on a suspension copolymer functionalised with 1,1'-carbonyldiimidazole further loaded with *Re* sub-nanometric structures was introduced into a column, playing a role of a PBR vessel. The column itself was constructed using stereolithography (SLA) photopolymerization, a variant of 3D printing technology. This technique is based on a beam of concentrated UV light or a laser focused onto a surface of a vat filled with liquid photopolymer. A shape is produced by means of cross-linking or degrading the polymer at the point of contact with the beam [24]. Although 3D printed, custom labware and "reactionware" concept may not exactly be new, in the present study the 3D printed parts served as entirely adjustable and easily scalable catalytic PBR that should enable simultaneous process of NACs remediation and AAMs production.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Reagents and materials

All of the reagents were of analytical grade or better. The materials used for the synthesis of heterogeneous catalysts as well as the materials used for the tests on the catalytic activity were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich Chemical Co. (Polish branch), and used as received. All other supportive reagents and solvents were acquired from Avantor Performance Materials Ltd. (Poland). Reverse Osmosis water was used through (Merck Milipore).

The materials for the 3-D printing setup, namely, building platforms, printing tanks as well as Clear v4 photocurable resin (Formlabs, MA, USA) were acquired from CAD Expert (Poland) and used as received.

2.2. Analytical methods

Phase composition of heterogeneous catalyst was identified using SPECS PHOIBOS-100 X-Ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). The analyses were carried out using hemispherical spectrometer equipped with a Mg X-ray source (1253.6 eV), operated at 250 W for the high-resolution spectra. The recorded spectra were fitted with the SPECLAB 2 and CasaXPS ver. 2.19 software, using the Gaussian-Lorentzian curve profile and the Shirley baseline. The C 1 s peak at 284.8 eV was used as the reference. To avoid differential charging of the sample surfaces, an

electron 'flood gun' was applied. The amount of *Re* loaded into heterogeneous catalyst was estimated using inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES, Agilent 5110 instrument). The morphology of the *Re* active sites loaded into matrix was assessed using FEI TITAN³ (FEI company, currently Thermo-Fisher) high resolution transmission electron microscope (HRTEM) equipped with a selected area electron diffractometer, EDX spectrometer, and high-angle annular dark-field (HAADF). Prior the analysis the polymer sample was embedded into EPON 812 resin (Serva, Germany), cut on Reichert-Jung Ultracut E (Leica) ultramicrotome and then placed on Cu/Formvar grids (100 mesh, Agar Scientific Ltd., Stansted, Great Britain). The rate of catalytic reactions was monitored using SPECORD 210 PLUS (Analytik-Jena, Jena, Germany) UV-Vis spectrophotometer (UV-Vis). The spectra were recorded in the range of 200–600 nm with a resolution of 1 nm.

2.3. Synthesis of the heterogeneous catalyst

The polymeric matrix used for the synthesis of heterogeneous catalyst was obtained as previously presented in the works cited under numbers [20,25]. Briefly, the expanded-gel structure vinylbenzyl chloride-co-divinylbenzene matrix (VBC-co-DVB) was synthesized *via* suspension polymerization technique in the presence of toluene. The VBC-co-DVB copolymer was then modified using 1,1'-carbonyldiimidazole (CDI) in the presence of dimethylformamide. Then, the ReO_4^- was loaded into the CDI-modified resin, by carrying out the ion exchange reaction between ReO_4^- and CDI functionalities, and the procedure was performed in the following way. First, NH_4ReO_4 solution containing $1000 \text{ mg Re L}^{-1}$ (1000 mL) was contacted with 2.5 g of anion exchange resin. This allowed to load ReO_4^- onto CDI functionalities. Then, the resin was separated from the solution by filtration on a frittered-glass funnel, and introduced into 1000 mL of water. This initiated the *in-situ* reduction of ReO_4^- *via* reduction-coupled adsorption according to the method shown previously [20,26]. The ReO_4^- -loaded polymer was kept in H_2O for 4 weeks. The swollen in H_2O catalyst was then used directly for further studies with no additional treatment nor material processing.

2.4. Catalytic hydrogenations of NACs obtained in batch mode

The catalytic reduction of NACs (batch mode) was carried out in quartz cuvette into which 2.5 mL of a NAC solution (0.1 mmol L^{-1}), 0.3 mL of NaBH_4 (0.1 mol L^{-1}), and 0.05 g of heterogeneous catalyst was added. The reaction was monitored by recording UV-Vis spectra at set time intervals. Based on these absorbances at λ_{max} : 410, 400, 400, 379 and 273 nm for 2-nitroaniline (2-NA), 4-nitrophenol (4-NP), 2,4,6-trinitrophenol (2,4,6-TNP), 4-nitroaniline (4-NA), nitrobenzene (NB), respectively, and at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 391 \text{ nm}$ for a sample containing an equimolar mix of all of the previous nitroarenes was determined.

The collected absorbances were then used for the modelling pseudo-first order kinetics of the reaction. Based on the Lambert-Beer law, it was assumed that ratio of NACs concentrations is equal to the ratio of their absorbances. Hence, the model was plotted as $-\ln(A_t/A_0)$ versus t (where A_t is the absorbance at time t and A_0 is the absorbance at the beginning of the process), and rate constants (k (min^{-1})) were evaluated from the slopes of these plots [25,26]. The first order rate constants (k_1) were then taken from the slope of the above-mentioned plots.

2.5. Packed bed reactor production and research setup for catalytic reduction of 4-nitrophenol (flow mode)

For the new process, a new packed bed reactor (PBR) loaded with *Re*-based heterogeneous catalyst was developed and applied for the flow-mode catalytic hydrogenation of 4-NP. The reaction was selected for this test because it can be considered as a model, occurring only in the presence of a catalyst with no possible reaction by-products.

The reactor was produced using stereolithography printing (SLA) 3D

technology. In the first stage, the column was designed using Autodesk Inventor Professional 2024 software, provided within educational license issued for the Wrocław University of Science and Technology. The simplified technical documentation of the designed column is presented in Fig. 1.

The PBR consisted of five 3-D printed parts. These include a column (diameter: 10 mm, length: 50 mm), in which the heterogenous catalyst compartment is contained (Fig. 1, part 3), sealing discs with pores of 0.1 mm diameter (2 pieces, Fig. 1, part 2), and sealing caps with column intakes (2 pieces, Fig. 1, part 1). All of initial CAD designs were exported to .stl files and prepared for production using Formlabs PreForm v.3.38.0 software. Then, the 3D printing was carried out with the aid of Formlabs Form3 3D SLA printer (MD, USA) using Formlabs Clear V4 photopolymer resin. Afterwards, the 3D prints were washed in isopropanol for 30 min using Formlabs FormWash device, and then cured with UV light at 60 °C in the Formlabs FormCure device. The produced

parts were then joined using designed M10×1 threads that were additionally sealed using CX-80 (Poland) HyperX polyurethane-based sealant.

Then, the 2.0 mL (1.46 g) of heterogenous catalyst was packed into PBR that was further set into the test setting, by connecting the PBR to a Masterflex MFLX07522 peristaltic pump in a way ensuring counter-gravitational flow through the PBR. The process was carried out at ambient temperature of 20 °C. The 600 catalyst bed volumes (BVs) of ice-cooled feed solution containing the mixture of 4-NP and NaBH₄ (1:100, mol:mol) was continuously fed into the PBR with the flow rate of 1.0 mL min⁻¹. The column effluent was collected in 10 mL portions using Büchi B-684 (Switzerland) fraction collector. The collected solutions were then analyzed using UV-Vis spectroscopy, and the absorbances (A) were measured at $\lambda_{\text{max}}=400$ nm, and used to calculate a mass balance of 4-NP conversion assuming that the ratio between equilibrium absorbance (A_e) in the effluent and absorbance in feed solution A₀, i.e.

Fig. 1. (A) Simplified technical documentation of 3-D printed column used as the PBR. (1) Sealing cap; (2) filter disc; (3) column. (B) research setup for the flow-mode process. (4) mixture of 4-nitrophenol and NaBH₄; (5) peristaltic pump; (6) PBR; (7) fraction collector. Graphics were rendered using Autodesk Inventor Professional 2024 software and bioRender under the license granted to Wrocław University of Science and Technology (Poland).

(A_e/A_0). (A_e/A_0) is equal to same 4-NP concentration ratio (C_e/C_0). Then, the so-processed data, were used to plot the catalytical column breakthrough function, linking the 4-NP reduction yield(%) with solution volume treated.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Catalyst characterization

To confirm the successful loading of *Re*-active species into the polymeric matrix, *Re* concentration, catalyst composition and *Re* morphology present in the samples were assessed by carrying out the ICP-OES, XPS and HRTEM/HAADF/EDS analyses.

Fig. 2 shows the *Re* 4f spectrum for rhenium, adsorbed on the surface of polymeric matrix together with its deconvolution into 4 components: Re^0 , ReO_2 , ReO_3 and Re_2O_7 , for which *Re* 4f_{7/2} electrons, are assigned to binding energies at 40.5, 42.2, 43.7 and 46.2 eV, respectively. The dominant form was *Re* at the +4 oxidation state, its share was estimated at 65.5 at%. Metallic rhenium also had a significant share of 18.5 at%. In general, the amount of *Re* loaded into the catalyst, when considered in terms of a mass, corresponds to 18.4 wt.% of *Re* ($0.184 \text{ g Re g}^{-1}$).

The XPS results indicate the presence of *Re* species in various oxidation states (Re^0 , Re^{+4} , Re^{+6} , and Re^{+7}), hence the active sites of *Re*-based catalyst may depend on the coexistence of these states. Because of this, the XPS spectra were also used to gain a closer understanding of the distribution of *Re* particles in the near-surface polymer layer. The structure of most outer layer of the '*Re*-modified polymer' was modelled using QUASES software [27]. Two different programs are included within the QUASES software package. Applied in this work, program 'Analyze', allows the user to model portions of the XPS spectral background using as variables the energy loss cross-section and the IMFP of the electron of interest. The IMFP values used during this analysis were calculated using the Tougaard TPP-2 M calculator provided with the QUASES software package. For examined sample, the energy loss cross section for polymers (model developed by Tougaard) was used. The results obtained for the sample analyzed in the 'as received' form are presented in Fig. 3.

The modeled spectra for C KLL, O KLL, N 1 s, and *Re* 4f, with the surface diagrams indicating the starting and ending depths, are displayed in Fig. 3. Carbon, as the main component of the polymeric matrix, is present in the entire bulk of the analyzed sample. However, its

Fig. 2. XPS *Re* 4f core level spectrum for examined nanocatalyst analyzed in 'as received' form.

Fig. 3. QUASES™ 'Analyze' modelled peaks of analyzed catalyst surface: C KLL, N 1 s, O KLL, and *Re* 4f using Mg K α source.

surface, as a result of contact with atmospheric air, contained additional amounts of the so-called contamination/adventitious carbon. The presence of carbon and its compounds throughout the depth profile of the sample is illustrated by the C KLL spectrum. In contrast, the thickness of the overlay attributed to carbon contamination was determined using the N 1 s spectrum. To fit the experimental data for N 1 s, a 'buried layer' model was used, assuming that 'polymeric nitrogen' (that is, bulk nitrogen) is covered by contamination carbon. The profile of the 'buried layer' models the energy lost by the photoelectrons emitted from atoms contained within a homogeneous layer as they pass through an overlying material of a different composition. Therefore, the thickness of that contamination layer was estimated to be around 0.4–0.5 nm.

Oxygen, like nitrogen and carbon, is a component of the examined polymer, so here, too, to fit the experimental data for the O KLL region, a 'buried layer' model was used. Analysis of the O KLL spectrum showed that oxygen began 0.1 nm below the sample surface; these results suggest that oxygen is a significant component of the contaminant layer, present as surface water, as well as typical C–OH, C = O and C(O)O bonds.

In the last step, an approximate depth to which the *Re* particles

penetrate the polymer was estimated, based on the fitting of the Re 4f peak after the extrinsic energy loss background was removed. Assuming that rhenium, like 'polymeric nitrogen', starts at a depth of 0.4 nm, this depth was estimated to be 8 nm. The calculated occurrence depth of Re_xO_y and Re^0 particles also limits their maximum size to 8 nm. This, in turn, suggests that similarly to our previous studies [20,25], Re could form particularly small structures. This was further verified by the HRTEM/HAADF analysis and these investigations indicate that the size of the Re_xO_y/Re nanoparticles was below 1 nm, being rather than nanoparticles Re atoms groupings.

Fig. 4 displays HRTEM/HAADF images aided by the EDS maps indicating the distribution of elements across the polymeric matrix.

As suggested by the XPS analysis and based on our previous studies [28], it was expected that Re will form particularly small structures, that imaging using traditional TEM would be impossible. Therefore, the electron microscopy imaging was carried out using HRTEM operating in scanning-transmission mode (STEM) using sensitive to atomic number HAADF detector. High-resolution STEM images (Fig. 4A) indicate the presence of subnanometric clusters with a high atomic number (i.e. Re) weakly bound to the polymer matrix, i.e. showing mobility under the influence of an electron beam. Based on these images, Re tends to form atom groupings that may be associated with the very beginning of nanoparticles formation. However, as can be seen in the images, these "apparent" ReNPs are still consisted of separate Re atoms, and no long-range ordering is observed.

The EDS maps (Fig. 4B) provides further insight into the samples composition. As can be seen in these, the N and Cl are equally distributed within the polymer. The observation was expected, as in the sample, N was derived from CDI functionalities, while Cl may be associated with the unreacted $-CH_2Cl$ groups within the matrix. Similar, equal distribution of Re is also observed, however a local congestion of Re is observed, where an "apparent" nanoparticle is being formed (Fig. 4B). In this context, similar, located in the same area congestion of O must be also noted. Although the O can be also linked to the CDI used for the

modification of polymeric matrix, the overlap of O and Re in the EDS maps suggest that the Re structures indeed consisted of Re oxides particles, as was suggested by the XPS analysis.

To sum up, as evidenced by the evaluation of phase composition and morphology of Re structures loaded into the polymer, the Re active sites base on the blend of various Re species, i.e. . These species tend to form widely dispersed structures that do not fit into the definition of a "nanoparticle", as the apparent size thereof are much below 1 nm. In this context, it is expected, that the synthesized heterogenous catalyst may reveal an outstanding catalytic activity, and as such may be a good fit for the flow mode hydrogenation processes.

3.2. First order kinetics modelling (batch mode)

For the evaluation of the catalyst activity, hydrogenation of selected NACs was carried out. Namely, the reductions of 4-NP, 4-NA, 2-NA, 2,4,6-TNP, NB and their mixture were carried out in a batch mode. To make the first-order modelling possible, the reactions were carried out applying excess of $NaBH_4$. UV-Vis spectra recorded for the catalytic reductions of NACs are displayed in Figures S2-S7. The first order rate constants (k_1), yields(%) and pseudo-first order kinetics plots of NACs conversions are displayed in Fig. 5. Additionally, Table 1 displays collected data of kinetics modelling.

As can be seen in Fig. 5B, all of the NACs were hydrogenated with the k_1 values of 0.062 (4-NP), 0.072 (4-NA), 0.058 (2-NA), 0.050 (NB), and 0.019 min^{-1} (2,4,6-TNP). Simultaneously, the reductions of 4-NP, 4-NA, 2-NA, and NB yielded 90–96 % conversions (Fig. 5C), while the reduction of 2,4,6-TNP was smaller and resulted with 66 % conversion. This phenomenon may be attributed to the number of nitro ($-NO_2$) groups to be reduced. Because 2,4,6-TNP contains 3 of them, the rate as well as the efficiency of its hydrogenation must had been lower than other NACs that contained only one nitro group per each NAC. The conclusion is further supported by the shape of first-order kinetics plot of 2,4,6-TNP reduction (Fig. 5A) that in contrast to all other tested NACs probably

Fig. 4. (A) STEM images of the heterogenous catalyst cross-section. (B) HRTEM/HAADF image used for EDS mapping, and EDS maps of Re , N, O, and Cl distribution across the cross-section.

Fig. 5. The catalytic hydrogenations of NACs: 4-nitrophenol (4-NP), 4-nitroaniline (4-NA), 2-nitroaniline (2-NA), nitrobenzene (NB), 2,4,6-trinitrophenol (2,4,6-TNP), and the mixture of these NACs. (A) Pseudo-first order kinetics plots; (B) first order rate constants calculated for maximum yields of conversions and for 50 % of NACs conversion; (C) maximum yields of NACs conversion. NACs concentration 0.1 mmol L^{-1} , NaBH_4 concentration: 0.1 mol L^{-1} , catalyst mass: 0.05 g

Table 1

First order kinetics data calculated for the catalytic hydrogenation of NACs.

NAC ^a	Substrate	Product	$k_1 \times 10^{-2b}$	R^2	$k_{1,50\%} \times 10^{-2c}$	R^2	Conv. ^d
4-NP		6.2	0.97	8.7	0.99	96.1	
4-NA		7.2	0.98	12.9	0.95	94.5	
2-NA		5.8	0.98	4.6	0.88	90.9	
NB		5.0	0.94	5.3	0.85	88.6	
2,4,6-TNP		1.9	0.97	2.6	0.99	66.7	
NACs mixture			1.4	0.90	2.9	0.96	78.6

^a NAC: nitroaromatic compound; 4-NP: 4-nitrophenol; 4-NA: 4-nitroaniline; 2-NA: 2-nitroaniline; NB: nitrobenzene; 2,4,6-TNP: 2,4,6-trinitrophenol.

^b first order kinetic rate constant (min^{-1}).

^c first order kinetic rate constant calculated for 50 % NAC conversion (min^{-1}).

^d maximum NAC conversion (%)

R^2 : correlation coefficient of fitting the first order kinetics.

involves a 2-stage process, the one with higher k_1 value (more negative slope), and the other with smaller k_1 (less negative slope). Because all other plots well fit into linear function for up to 60 min of the process (Fig. 5A), the two-stage reaction of 2,4,6-TNP reduction occurring at 40 min cannot be associated with depletion of NaBH_4 . This may suggest, that the 2,4,6-TNP must had experienced diffusion limitations in the polymeric network of the heterogenous catalyst, and again, it may be attributed to the structure of 2,4,6-TNP itself.

These observations can be further extended to the reaction carried out for the mixture of all tested NACs (Fig. 5). Both, rate constant (0.014

min^{-1} , Fig. 5B) as well as reduction yield (78 %, Fig. 5C) are significantly smaller as compared to other NACs. However, because these values are still higher than for 2,4,6-TNP hydrogenation, it may be concluded that 2,4,6-TNP as a part of NACs mixture is the reason for this behavior. Simply, the 4-NP, 4-NA, 2-NA, and NB loaded in the mixture are hydrogenated faster, and once their reduction is completed there must be still 2,4,6-TNP to be processed.

In general, based on the obtained data, it may be concluded that the *Re*-loaded catalyst reveal significant catalytic activity in the processes of NACs hydrogenation. The reason for this may be found in the samples

morphology and composition. First, the high dispersion of *Re*-based catalysts is a significant factor contributing to their catalytic activity. Second, mixed-valency of the produced *Re* active sites might contribute to the catalysts robustness. Third, the affinity of styrene-base matrix to nitroaromatics might contribute to overcoming potential diffusion limitations. Although it is impossible to consider these factors separately, the general effect is that the overall catalytic activity is very high. This further implies that the developed catalyst is suitable for the continuous flow-mode processes.

3.3. Flow mode catalytic hydrogenation of 4-nitrophenol

Based on the results discussed above, the synthesis of heterogenous catalyst was successful. To verify, whether the obtained catalytical materials is a good fit for a flow-mode process, it has been packed into 3-D printed column (Fig. 1) to form a PBR. The so-prepared PBR was then set into a flow-mode system, and 600 BVs of 4-NP was passed through it. Then, the collected effluent was analysed at $\lambda_{\max}=400$ nm, and the gathered data were plotted into $C_e/C_0=f(\text{BV})$ function. The collected and re-calculated data are presented in Fig. 6.

Based on Fig. 6A, the proportion of unprocessed 4-NP consistently increased with the number of bed volumes (BVs) passing through the PBR, showing a strong linear trend. By integrating the area above the experimental linear fit in Fig. 6A [29], it was determined that during the breakthrough test, a total of 394.6 mmol of 4-NP was processed. This corresponds to 197.3 mmol of 4-NP processed per BV. However, the breakthrough test was conducted until 62 % column leakage was reached. Assuming a stricter criterion of only 5 % 4-NP leakage, the column would be able to treat up to 46 BVs. Under these conditions, using a theoretical column with a 10 L capacity, the processed 4-NP solution volume would be total of 460 L before reaching the 5 % leakage threshold.

The aforementioned considerations relate to a scenario, in which the catalytical process would be aimed at elimination of 4-NP from.. The situation would be different if the process' purpose would be to produce as much 4-AP as possible. In this context, the process could be carried out until entire depletion of PBR catalytical activity (namely, up to 100 % 4-NP breakthrough). Hence, the data presented in Fig. 6A, were used to model the theoretical capacity of the PBR, and the anticipated column behavior is displayed in Fig. 6C. Based on the data presented, the theoretical 100 % of column breakthrough is expected to occur at 909 BVs, which in the experimental conditions would correspond to 1.8 L of the applied 4-NP solution. Based on these and the integration of the area above the model, it may be concluded, that such a process would process ~472 mmol of 4-NP. Because the hydrogenation of 4-NP is a model reaction which does not generate any by-products, it can be stated that the estimated molarity of 4-NP processed would be equal to the 4-AP

produced. Further, 472 mmol of 4-AP would be equivalent to 51.5 g of this fine chemical product.

As the last part of the considerations on the reaction, the Fig. 6B displays change of k_1 over volume of 4-NP passed. These values were fitted using logarithmic function, that R^2 value fits into the definition of a "good fit". The exponential form of this equation allowed to determine the $k(V)=e^bBV^a$ function, where b , and a are intercept and slope of the logarithmic function. Based on this it was estimated that the PBR lost 60 % of its catalytic activity after treating 100 BVs of the 4-NP solution. This estimation opens a path for further optimizations, and indicate, that there is a room for optimizations that could lead to higher efficiencies of the proposed flow-mode catalytical system.

The developed process was also set in the context of other works focusing on the flow-mode processes of nitroaromatic compounds reduction. The data found in other research are displayed in Table 2. Based on this review of literature the proposed solution proposes a significant advancement in the concept of carrying out the process. As compared to others, the designed column enables processing of high volumes of solution containing 4-NP with additional difference, that the concentration thereof is way greater than these applied in the other works.

This positive effect observed in the presented technology may be attributed to the greater values of liquid hour space velocity (LHSV) applied in the current study as compared to others (Table 2). In simplified terms, the value estimates the regents-catalytical bed contact time. However, when compared to other studies, the proposed catalytical bed still offers an outstanding catalytical capacity that opens a path for further optimizations which could be aimed and increasing process efficiency. At this point, it must be also noticed that the presented technology involves the application of NaBH_4 for the in-situ generation of H_2 gas being a reduction carrier. Although NaBH_4 is toxic, and causes potential problems with separation thus contributing to water pollution, the in-situ generation of H_2 allows to omit using sophisticated, pressurized equipment, and allow to control the amount of H_2 introduced into the system, and thus, to avoid gas wastage. Further, there are examples of technologies where NaBH_4 was used a clean source of H_2 generation in fuel cells. The same approach could be applied in the nitroaromatics reduction, where it would be possible to transform NaBH_4 to non-toxic sodium borate [5].

4. Conclusion

The synthesis of a unique heterogeneous catalyst with *Re*-active sites within a suspension copolymer functionalized with 1,1'-carbonyldiimidazole was successful, showcasing significant potential for the catalytic reduction of nitroaromatic compounds (NACs). The XPS and HRTEM/HAADF analyses confirmed the presence and distribution of *Re*

Fig. 6. (A) Catalytic column breakthrough curve; (B) change of the rate constant; (C) modelled column capacity. Concentration of 4-NP in feed solution: 0.1 mmol L^{-1} , $\text{BV}=2$ mL, feed flow rate: 1 mL min^{-1} .

Table 2

Collation of various nitro-compound hydrogenation processes and their catalytic capabilities.

Hydrogenated nitro-compound	Catalyst	Process information	LHSV [hr^{-1}]	Stationary apparent reaction constant k_1 [min^{-1}]	Breakthrough point*		Total conversion to breakthrough		Ref.
					Bed volumes	$n_{\text{substrate}} V_{\text{bed}}^{-1}$ [mmol cm^{-3}]	[%]	[mmol]	
Nitrobenzene (NB)	Fe^0 1–2 mm	$V_{\text{bed}} = 197.82 \text{ cm}^3$; $C_{\text{NB}} = 1 \text{ mM}$	0.849–0.940	no data	600	no data	>95	>112.76	[30]
2-nitrotoluene (2-NT)	Fe^0 <300 μm	$V_{\text{bed}} = 1.57 \text{ cm}^3$; $V_{\text{pores}} = 0.96 \text{ cm}^3$; $C_{2\text{-NT}} = 98.6 \mu\text{M}$	15.287	2.6	560	33.76	100	0.05	[31]
Nitrobenzene (NB)	Anaerobic bacteria, Fe^0 1 mm/sand 1:30 v/v	$V_{\text{bed}} = 94.2 \text{ cm}^3$; $V_{\text{pores}} = 32.3 \text{ cm}^3$; $C_{\text{NB}} = 80 \mu\text{M}$	0.318	no data	1500 / 3064**	41.15 / 84.05**	>75	>2.91	[32]
Nitroguanidine (NQ)***	Fe^0 >44 μm /sand 1:1 v/v	$V_{\text{bed}} = 2 \text{ cm}^3$; $V_{\text{pores}} = 1.49 \text{ cm}^3$; $C_{\text{NQ}} = 1 \text{ mM}$	0.333	0.017	490	> 365.05	>99	>0.72	[33]
Nitrobenzene (NB)	Pd nanospheres 3.7 nm	Membrane reactor; $A_{\text{membrane}} = 5 \text{ cm}^2$; $\text{Load}_{\text{Pd}} = 1.09 \mu\text{g cm}^2$; $C_{\text{NB}} = 30 \text{ mM}$; $Q = 15 \mu\text{L min}^{-1}$	N/A	no data	<7 h****	N/A	>95	>0.03	[34]
4-nitrophenol (4-NP)	Re sub-nanometric catalyst	$V_{\text{bed}} = 2.0 \text{ cm}^3$; $C_{4\text{-NP}} = 0.1 \text{ mM}$	30	0.078	50 *-909**	197**	96.5	7.92	This work

* Point to which conversion was total.

** Point where conversion completely halted.

*** Aliphatic compound.

**** Total conversion duration.

species within the polymer matrix, indicating the formation of *Re* oxides and metallic *Re* at sub-nanometric scales, enhancing the catalytic activity. The batch mode experiments demonstrated that the catalyst efficiently reduced various NACs, including 4-NP, 4-NA, 2-NA, NB, and 2,4,6-TNP, with high conversion yields and rate constants, particularly noting the diffusion limitations associated with multi-nitro compounds like 2,4,6-TNP.

The integration of the *Re*-based catalyst into a 3D-printed packed bed reactor (PBR) enabled effective flow-mode processing, where the hydrogenation of 4-NP was carried out efficiently, indicating the potential for large-scale applications. The linear increase in unprocessed 4-NP during the breakthrough tests and the theoretical capacity model suggest that the PBR can handle substantial volumes of NAC-contaminated solutions before significant leakage occurs. These findings underscore the catalyst's applicability in industrial synthesis of aromatic amines (AAMs), providing a more environmentally friendly and efficient alternative to traditional methods.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Piotr Cyganowski: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Włodzimierz Tylus:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation. **Sebastian Kinas:** Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Piotr Jamróz:** Validation, Supervision, Resources, Formal analysis.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.cep.2024.110141](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cep.2024.110141).

Data availability

The data are stored under permanent identifier <https://doi.org/10.18150/DD20A7>

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